

Policy brief – Deliverable 8.3

EU funds for inclusive labour markets

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European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Policy brief: EU funds for inclusive labour markets

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[PATHS2INCLUDE](#) is a 3-year research project funded by Horizon Europe that investigates 1. the multi-dimensional aspects of discrimination, 2. policies that could reduce inequalities and promote social inclusion in European labour markets and 3. risk factors of vulnerability that may arise in the future of work. The research focuses on three key labour-market processes: recruitment; career paths; and exit from working life, giving particular attention to labour-market participation at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, age, health, disability, and care responsibilities.

1. Introduction

Inclusive labour markets are more productive and resilient to demographic shifts as well as social and economic challenges, however, many social groups continue to experience discrimination and disadvantages in the European Union (EU) labour market. The implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights has the potential to redress the situation and has launched a number of initiatives over the last years (European Commission, 2021; Rossenbacker & Gosme, 2025).

The Pillar consists of twenty principles and rights to support well-functioning and fair labour markets and welfare systems, structured around three categories: equal opportunities and access to the labour market, fair working conditions, and social protection and inclusion. To implement these principles, a subsequent Action Plan sets out a number of EU actions and three EU headline targets to be achieved by the end of 2030, including increasing the employment rate to at least 78% (of the population aged 20 to 64) by 2030. (European Commission, 2021)

This goal is crucial in light of demographic changes and a shrinking work-age population and can only be achieved by reaching out to the groups that continue to be vulnerable to disadvantages in the labour market, including women, migrant workers and older workers. The European Commission is therefore striving to promote greater labour market participation by as many working-age individuals as possible, by removing existing barriers and reaching out to groups with fewer opportunities.

To achieve its goal, **the EU needs a strong budget** aligned with policies that target underrepresented groups, promote equal opportunities, and support systemic change in the labour market. In July 2025, the European Commission proposed the seven-year Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for the period of 2028-2034 (European Commission, 2025a). This package includes proposals to allocate funds to help deliver on the European Pillar of Social Rights by investing in people through quality employment, social inclusion, education and skills. The next step consists of discussing and finding an agreement with the European Parliament and Council of the EU on the future budget by the end of 2027. The new MFF offers an opportunity to reinstate the EU's commitment to growing the employment rate by 2030 and set new priorities and intensify efforts towards more inclusive labour markets and equal opportunities for all.

This policy brief aims to serve as a bridge between research and policy. Based on evidence from PATHS2INCLUDE research, it serves to guide policy makers, funding programme designers, and civil society actors in leveraging EU funding instruments to address structural labour market vulnerabilities stemming from age, gender, caregiving responsibilities, health limitations, and ethnicity.

2. Why inclusive labour markets matter

Although several European countries have experienced economic growth and more diversity in their workforces, numerous social groups (such as women, migrants, persons with health issues, and older workers) continue to face disadvantages in the labour market (European Commission, 2021). Making labour markets more inclusive, however, is not only a moral imperative but also an economic necessity. The experience of temporary exclusion from the labour market heightens the risk of long-term unemployment and labour market inactivity, which is detrimental for productive labour markets. Workers who lack access to decent work, or whose rights are not respected both within and beyond the workplace, are less likely to achieve their full productive potential, which in turn weakens innovation and long-term economic growth (PATHS2INCLUDE, 2025). More specifically, discrimination hinders equal opportunities and forces people in roles below their skills level. It can lead to workplace underperformance due to mental health strain, and reduce economic development when individuals exit the labour market as they are convinced that their efforts will not be fairly compensated (OECD, 2025a). In addition, unstable labour market attachment can enhance people's feelings of being excluded from society and, on a larger scale, lessen social cohesion, increase discontent, and reduce peoples' trust in employers, governments and institutions (Eurofound, 2023).

Demographic ageing presents a further challenge. As Europe's population grows older, its working population grows smaller with pension systems under increasing pressure. This has led to the introduction of policies aimed at extending working lives, though these measures do not benefit all older workers equally, such as those with health limitations or a low income. Ongoing socio-economic disparities in many societies continue to pose a significant barrier to achieving longer working lives (Vasile et al., 2025). According to the OECD (2025b), population ageing could lead to the GDP per capita growth slowing down by about 40% if no policy action is taken. At the same time, the trend of a shrinking labour force contributes to skills shortages and mismatches, leading to a declining global competitiveness. **Building inclusive labour markets is therefore both a strategic necessity both for Europe's future social and economic well-being.** Although achieving longer working lives is a crucial policy ambition, it should be accompanied by achieving better working lives as well.

Implementing activation policies alone do not suffice. While they foster labour market engagement, they do not guarantee job creation or employment stability. Instead, they may exacerbate inequalities if structural labour market deficiencies, such as skill mismatches, discrimination, or a lack of sufficient job opportunities, are not adequately addressed (Ciani & Vivoli, 2025). Developing a truly inclusive labour market requires a comprehensive policy approach that tackles these systemic issues and supports individuals throughout their working lives. The following section highlights some key EU funding instruments that can facilitate pathways toward more inclusive labour markets.

3. EU funding programmes for inclusive labour markets.

The following section identifies key European Union funding mechanisms and discusses their relevance to address the challenges faced by persons in vulnerable situations when accessing the labour market, as identified in PATHS2INCLUDE research.

3.1. European Social Fund Plus

While different EU funds provide direct and indirect support to workers, one particular fund stands out in providing direct support through projects which promote employment, social inclusion, health and education: the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+). The ESF+ is explicitly mentioned in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Title XI) and is a key stream of the 2021-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework, the EU's 7-year budget (European Commission, 2025b).

The ESF+ is the European Union's most important instrument for Member States to co-finance actions aimed at implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights and its accompanying Action Plan, by fighting poverty and exclusion, combating discrimination, and helping the most disadvantaged groups to gain access to the labour market.

The latest annual Joint Employment Report provides examples of how Member States have introduced hiring incentives and subsidies for job creation, with a focus on promoting employment in key sectors and supporting disadvantaged groups. For instance, in Malta, the A2E Scheme, co-financed by the ESF+ and Malta's Government, will run until 2029 and offers financial support to employers for hiring disadvantaged individuals and thereby promoting a more diverse and inclusive workforce (European Commission, 2025c).

Another use of the ESF+ for boosting inclusive labour markets are initiatives to foster cross-country cooperation between ESF+ authorities to develop transnational projects. For instance, a call was issued in 2025 to transfer or scale up social innovations referenced in the Disability Employment Package. Applicants were expected to base their proposals on one or more specific practices presented in the Package, with the goal of improving employment opportunities for persons with disabilities – such as recruitment and career guidance, inclusive hiring, reasonable accommodation at work, retention, return to work, or transition from sheltered employment to the open labour market (ESF+ & Social Innovation Plus Initiative, 2025).

PATHS2INCLUDE research found that labour market exclusion is not only understood as the result of individual factors, such as gender, age, and migrant status, but also relates to contextual characteristics and their intersections throughout the life course of people, such as leaving education, caregiving responsibilities, organisational features, and health-related work interruptions. Policies should therefore address both the individual and contextual level. The current and future ESF+ could go further to ensure non-discrimination, promote gender equality, improve equality mainstreaming and strengthen the labour market participation of women and disadvantaged groups, by fostering equal opportunities and career progression, ensuring equal

pay for equal work, or work of equal value, transparency in pay structures, and promoting the reconciliation of work, family and private life – including through access to affordable and high-quality care (early childhood education and care, and long-term care), and family-related leave and flexible working arrangements for parents and other informal carers, in line with the European Care Strategy (European Commission, 2022a), as well as by ensuring accessibility in the work place.

3.2. Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme

The Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values (CERV) programme, running from 2021-2027, aims to support rights-based, democratic, equal and inclusive societies based on the rule of law by protecting and promoting the rights and values enshrined in EU Treaties and the Charter of Fundamental Rights (European Commission, 2025d). The CERV programme has four pillars, of which the first one is especially relevant to creating more inclusive labour markets: Equality, Rights and Gender Equality. It offers opportunities for national or transnational partnerships to drive change through social innovation, exchange of good practice and more. This includes opportunities to foster more inclusive labour markets, including for women.

The European Commission committed to halving the gender employment gap by 2030, compared to 2019 (European Commission, 2021). PATHS2INCLUDE findings indeed highlight important gender disparities in European labour markets, with women, and particularly those with dependents, less likely to be active in the labour market than men (Valls et al., 2025), and mothers—especially single mothers—facing significant disadvantages in the recruitment process (Buttler et al., 2025a). These differences reflect the continuing influence of gendered caregiving responsibilities and result in a large untapped potential for our economies. The European Institute for Gender Equality, for instance, estimated that substantial gender equality improvements could lead to an employment rate of 80% by 2050 (EIGE, 2017).

To mobilise the female workforce, amongst other measures, governments must combat discrimination in hiring by encouraging employers, public authorities, and social partners to adopt concrete, actionable diversity policy measures as well as expand flexible work arrangements to facilitate work-life balance and prevent care-based discrimination.

The 2025 CERV call for projects has the aim of “promoting diversity management and inclusion at the workplace, both in the public and private sector” (European Commission, 2025e). Projects should promote diversity and inclusion at the workplace via an intersectional approach, and the objective of the call is to strengthen the Diversity Charters network, supporting the implementation and further development of existing Diversity Charters in the EU and increasing the number of their signatories.

One strand of the PATHS2INCLUDE research focused on identifying the organisational-level determinants of care-based discrimination, highlighting effective diversity measures that can prevent discrimination (Buttler et al., 2025a). The CERV programme and its 2025 call thus

provide a concrete policy avenue to translate this evidence into coordinated action for more gender-equal and inclusive labour markets across the EU.

3.3. Recovery and Resilience Facility

PATHS2INCLUDE examined vulnerability in the future of work by studying the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and of digitization and automation. The research found that labour market vulnerability across Europe is influenced by broader contextual factors, including global crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. The comparison between pre-pandemic and pandemic periods reveals that existing inequality became more visible after the pandemic, particularly for older women and those with health problems (Alecú et al., 2025). Not only consequences of the pandemic and the following economic downturn, but also digitalisation introduces barriers and exacerbates existing inequalities for at-risk groups (Valls et al., 2024).

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic and other crises, the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) fund was established to create a stronger and more resilient Europe by making economies and societies more sustainable, resilient and prepared for the green and digital transition. Initiatives under the RRF must address policy areas such as the digital transformation; smart, sustainable and inclusive growth; and social and territorial cohesion (European Commission, 2025f). According to the European Commission, many reforms carried out through the RRF have aimed to improve skills and labour market outcomes. These include initiatives to strengthen education systems, improve labour market functioning, and enhance the sustainability of social security and pension systems.

For example, supported by the RRF, Portugal established the Sustainable Employment Commitment programme, offering financial subsidies and social security reductions to employers to support the creation of 30 000 permanent jobs, reduce labour market segmentation, and promote gender equality while facilitating youth integration into the labour market (European Commission, 2025c). In addition, France introduced reforms to support jobseekers, including by improving trainings and providing more support especially for vulnerable groups (European Commission, 2025g).

From the onset, the RRF was set up as a temporary instrument ending in 2026. As the end of the instrument is now within sight, the European Commission stands ready to work with Member States to ensure a smooth and successful closure of the instrument and has encouraged Member States to make full use of the potential of this instrument (European Commission, 2025h).

3.4. European Regional Development Fund

The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) aims to reduce economic, social and territorial disparities across EU regions (European Commission, 2025i). Investments aim to make Europe more social by supporting effective and inclusive employment, education, skills and social inclusion. It is a major financial instrument of the European Union aimed at strengthening economic and social cohesion by correcting imbalances in between regions. It supports various projects that can have a significant impact on workers in vulnerable situations by providing

financial support for infrastructure development, for example, care infrastructure such as childcare centres, schools, community centres and more (Gosme et al., 2025).

The 2021 ERDF regulation states that “the ERDF should support and promote transition from institutional to family-based or community-based care through supporting facilities that would seek to prevent segregation from the community, would facilitate the integration of people in society and would seek to ensure independent living conditions” (European Union, 2021). Indeed, the ERDF is used to support the transition from institutional to community, family-based care for children with disabilities through investments in supported living, accessible housing, housing adaptations, non-segregated social housing within the community; accessibility of services and the built environment (public transport, public buildings, etc.); technical aids and assistive technologies. The availability of these services can alleviate employment barriers for individuals with caregiving responsibilities, workers with disabilities and workers in migration, and support them settling into their host communities.

The integration of people with a migrant background is also included within the scope of support provided through the ERDF (European Commission, 2022b). One specific example is “Neighbourhood mothers”, known as “Stadtteilmütter in Neukölln” in Germany, which is a grassroots outreach project aimed at facilitating access to information and services to help families from immigrant backgrounds with young children up to 12 years old. It was launched in 2004 in Berlin’s Neukölln area with 12 Turkish mothers receiving training to support newly arriving mothers. It has now become a network of over 70 neighbourhood mothers from all different nationalities to help integrate families and create a cohesive community (European Commission, 2018).

The PATHS2INCLUDE research findings indeed highlight how disadvantages experienced over the working life are embedded in national and regional contexts. Structural and institutional contexts, for example economic structures and public policies, influence the effects of individual-level characteristics that may create labour market vulnerability. Depending on their design and implementation, they can either mitigate or increase the disadvantages faced by groups in vulnerable situations. For example, higher regional education levels generally improve labour market activation rates and regions with increased investments in Active Labour Market Policies (ALMPs) have higher employment rates (Vivoli et al., 2024). This indicates that investments in individuals must be integrated with local industrial and development policies and investments, for example, as part of the ERDF.

3.5. Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

The Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) aims to strengthen national capacities for migration management and promote solidarity and responsibility sharing among EU Member States, particularly through emergency assistance and relocation. Initiatives funded by AMIF are diverse but include supporting integration measures such as professional guidance (European Commission, 2025j). It is not a fund focusing specifically on employment but plays a complementary role in making labour markets more inclusive, especially by supporting the integration into labour markets of third-country nationals. The support can include funding for

language courses, skills assessments and orientation programmes that are often pre-requisites before migrant workers can access training or employment. It can also help them understand labour rights, local job markets and services, breaking down barriers to accessing employment.

In 2023, a call was published for proposals on ‘multi-stakeholder initiatives for migrant integration into the labour market’ resulting in eight transnational projects that kicked off in spring 2024 and are currently under implementation (European Commission, 2025c). In April 2025, a new AMIF call was published focusing on initiatives aiming to improve female migrants’ integration and improving migrants’ digital skills (European Commission, 2025k).

AMIF’s funding priorities align closely with the persistent challenges highlighted PATHS2INCLUDE research, particularly as these indicate that ethnic discrimination remains prevalent across Europe limiting access to equal employment opportunities. Factorial studies found that applicants from other nationalities than the host country experience systemic biases during the hiring process, particularly from more culturally distant countries. Across all countries included in the study, immigrants faced significantly lower hiring chances, regardless of their language skills or education origin, indicating potential nationality-based discrimination (Buttler et al., 2025b). At the same time, including migrants and their significantly untapped potential into the labour market in a sustainable way is crucial for combating skills shortages and fostering economic growth and social cohesion in the host countries (European Commission, 2025l).

PATHS2INCLUDE findings also highlight a range of organisational-level measures that employers can implement to reduce ethnic discrimination in hiring, namely by offering training opportunities to all employees, making hiring decisions collectively, implementing hiring practices that are attentive to diversity, mentoring or buddy programmes as well as support programmes for foreign employees (Buttler et al., 2025b). These findings underscore the importance of initiatives like those funded by AMIF, which not only address structural barriers but also promote inclusive employment practices across Europe.

4. Recommendations

Based on our research findings, we provide the following recommendations for mainstreaming actions in the current and future EU budget to reduce inequalities in European labour markets.

- It is recommended to ensure full alignment of the new **European Social Fund Plus** with the goals of the European Care Strategy (to boost early childhood education and care, long-term care and support to informal carers) alleviating employment barriers for people with caregiving responsibilities, with a clear allocation of funds for social and care objectives under the next EU budget. The capacity of Public Employment Services should also be reinforced through the ESF, enabling them to provide tailored support to both employers in their hiring practices and to workers in vulnerable situations.
- It is recommended to continue funding **CERV** transnational actions and projects to promote diversity in the workplace, through a mix of research, capacity-building, good practice exchanges and awareness-raising campaigns targeting employers and employees. These should focus on inclusive practices upon labour market entry, within employment and

labour market exit processes and prioritise facilitating the labour market access of mothers, one of the most vulnerable groups identified in PATHS2INCLUDE research.

- With just over a year left to make full use of this temporary financial instrument, it is recommended that Member States and European Commission use the **RRF** to trigger a profound rethink of the workplace towards the green and digital transition, with a mix of initiatives promoting diversity and inclusion as well as tailored upskilling and training programmes for workers in vulnerable situations.
- Continued investments (under the current and future EU budget) are needed in care and education infrastructure in both urban and rural **regions** of the European Union, as well as infrastructure investments to support Active Labour Market Policies aimed at supporting labour market inclusion of people in more marginalised communities. This can include targeted investments for local community/civil society organisations representing and working with such communities, initiatives to foster new partnerships between such organisations and regional-level labour market stakeholders like Public Employment Services.
- The **AMIF** would benefit from continued investments in inclusive labour market practices, namely focused on measures to reduce bias in hiring, promote the adoption of concrete, actionable measures like inclusive hiring practices, mentoring programmes, and diversity management training to engage managers in diversity efforts.

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[PATHS2INCLUDE](#) is a 3-year research project funded by Horizon Europe that investigates 1. the multi-dimensional aspects of discrimination, 2. policies that could reduce inequalities and promote social inclusion in European labour markets and 3. risk factors of vulnerability that may arise in the future of work. The research focuses on three key labour-market processes: recruitment; career paths; and exit from working life, giving particular attention to labour-market participation at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, age, health, disability, and care responsibilities.

1. Introduction

The [European Pillar of Social Rights](#) includes twenty principles and rights to support well-functioning and fair labour markets and welfare systems, structured around three categories: equal opportunities and access to the labour market, fair working conditions, and social protection and inclusion. To implement these principles, the [Action Plan](#) sets out a number of EU actions and three EU headline targets to be achieved by the end of 2030 in the areas of employment, skills, and social protection.

One of the targets aims to increase the employment rate to at least 78% (of the population aged 20 to 64) by 2030. To achieve this goal, the European Commission is striving to promote greater participation in the labour market by as many working-age individuals as possible, by removing existing barriers and reaching out to groups with fewer opportunities (European Commission, 2021). Nevertheless, the latest European Commission's Employment and Social Developments report highlights that one-fifth of the working-age population, around 51 million people, are currently outside the labour market (European Commission, 2025a).

This persistent exclusion is harmful to the EU economy and societal unity as it may lead individuals into roles beneath their skills level, contribute to workplace underperformance, discourage labour market participation and misallocate talent, eroding social cohesion and diminishing both civic engagement and community development (OECD, 2025).

Expanding the labour force by increasing the participation of underrepresented groups enhances productivity and strengthens the resilience of labour markets to demographic shifts. This reduces pressure on pension systems, healthcare, and public finances, making it a vital step towards boosting the EU's long-term competitiveness and preparedness for future economic and social challenges.

In June 2025, the European Commission launched a public consultation on the new European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan that would be finished by the end of 2025. In response, this EU policy brief draws on PATHS2INCLUDE findings to fill in gaps in data and provide policy recommendations for promoting inclusive labour markets, with the aim of implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights principles. The recommendations are especially relevant for the following Pillar Principles: 1. Education, training and life-long learning, 2. Gender Equality, 3. Equal opportunities, 4. Active support to employment, 6. Wages, 9. Work-life balance, and 10. Healthy, safe and well-adapted work environment.

2. Main findings

The following section discusses the main findings of the PATHS2INCLUDE research, highlighting persisting issues in the context of labour market outcomes of groups in vulnerable situations.

2.1. Education and skills development can offset effects of disadvantages

The EU target of adults participating in training every year is set for at least 60% by 2030. However, by 2022 only 39,5% of adults were participating in learning activities (excluding guided on-the-job training) each year (European Commission, 2025b). For low-qualified adults this rate only reached 18%. PATHS2INCLUDE findings confirm the importance of reaching the higher training target by showcasing the strong correlation between higher education levels and increased labour market participation and employment. In particular, tertiary education emerged as a key factor that can partially mitigate the impact of structural disadvantages related to gender and health on labour market attachment (Valls et al., 2025). In addition, education became increasingly important for navigating the post-pandemic labour market that is shaped by digitalisation and flexible work arrangements, disproportionately benefiting those in higher-skilled occupations.

Moreover, research findings highlight that for individuals with health limitations¹, labour market attachment is closely related to their skills, even if they stay in the same occupation (Lipowska & Palczyńska, 2025). This indicates that enhancing skills may improve their employment situation without needing to change occupations. Since people with health limitations may have fewer opportunities to change occupations, policies supporting the development of digital and social skills could help reduce the negative effects of health limitations on labour market participation.

2.2. Gender inclusive labour markets

By 2030, the European Commission aims to at least halve the gender employment gap compared to 2019 (European Commission, 2021). PATHS2INCLUDE findings, however, show that women, and particularly those with dependents, are generally less likely to be active in the labour market than men, differences that most likely reflect the continuing influence of gendered caregiving

¹ The variable 'health limitation' is measured by the respondent's self-assessment of whether he/she is limited (in "activities people usually do") by any on-going physical, mental or emotional health problem, including disease or impairment, and old age. Consequences of injuries/accidents, congenital conditions, etc., are all included. Only the limitations directly caused by or related to one or more health problems are considered. In this context, disabilities are considered as being the consequence of health problems, and limitations due to disabilities are taken into account as being caused by health problems (Eurostat, 2021).

responsibilities (Valls et al., 2025). Moreover, research results show a gendered parenthood penalty, with mothers—especially single mothers—facing significant disadvantages in the recruitment process (Buttler et al., 2025). Despite an overall increased female labour force participation, gender wage gaps and barriers to career advancement remain significant.

The research also emphasises the economic vulnerability of women in retirement. Men and women display similar retirement intentions but when other risk factors, such as caregiving responsibilities, health limitations and low socio-economic status, are taken into consideration, women are more likely than men to indicate the intention to retire early (Vasile et al., 2025). This often goes with fragmented career paths and lower earnings resulting in lower retirement savings which might lead to financial gender gaps and insecurity in older age.

2.3. Persistent gaps in data availability

As part of the research, EU and national surveys were analysed to assess their ability to identify at-risk groups in the labour market. The findings highlight the difficulty of identifying these groups, the discrimination they may face, and their poor labour market integration, due to several factors such as limited sample sizes or lack of specific questions (Valls et al., 2024). Although some surveys incorporate questions designed to capture data on at-risk groups or phases of life, the scope and generalisability of the results is often limited. This lack of comprehensive data poses a crucial challenge in accurately assessing the impact of employment policies on at-risk groups. A more comprehensive data collection would enable EU policy makers to better understand the challenges faced by at-risk groups and effectively tailor interventions to promote inclusive and equitable employment opportunities across different stages of the working life, as well as prepare policies to decrease vulnerability in the future of work.

2.4. Intersecting disadvantages shape labour market exclusion

PATHS2INCLUDE research shows that being at risk of labour market exclusion is not only based on individual characteristics such as gender, age, education, or migrant background, but often relates to contextual characteristics and their interplay and intersection throughout the life course of people. For example, women with health limitations living in households with dependents faced especially high barriers to labour market attachment (Valls et al., 2025). These factors combine to create specific challenges and barriers to labour market entry, stability, and progression. Policies designed to strengthen labour market attachment need to look at the intersectional nature of disadvantage, as one-size-fits-all approaches are likely to be inadequate considering such complexity. Alternatively, inclusive measures need to target overlapping vulnerabilities, supporting not only older workers or individuals with health limitations, but also recognising how these characteristics intersect with gender, caregiving responsibilities, and education.

2.5. Discrimination in recruitment remains prevalent across Europe

EU law sets minimum requirements on the equal treatment of persons regardless of sex, ethnic or racial origin, disability, religion or belief, age and sexual orientation.² However, our research findings confirm that mothers and ethnic minorities continue to experience systemic biases across Europe which limits equal access to employment opportunities, aligning with outcomes of the latest report on the application of the Directives (European Commission, 2021b). Across all countries included in our research, immigrants faced significantly lower hiring chances, regardless of their language skills or education origin indicating potential nationality-based discrimination (Rogstad et al., 2025). Another group particularly subject to hiring discrimination are single mothers (Buttler et al., 2025). The analysis focused specifically on the organisational features that shape this discrimination, finding that comprehensive organisational support and inclusive hiring practises can contribute to a more diverse workforce (Rogstad et al., 2025). Collective recruitment panels, flexible work arrangements, concrete diversity measures (such as inclusive hiring procedures, mentoring or buddy programmes) a transparent assessment of soft skills, and training opportunities are some of the initiatives identified to reduce hiring discrimination.

2.6. Activating older workers may increase inequalities

Encouraging older workers to postpone retirement may increase inequalities as not all workers have equal opportunities to adjust their timing of retirement and extend their working life. For workers in vulnerable situations, disadvantages tend to accumulate over the life course, making a disproportionate impact on their quality of life in older age. An analysis of SHARE data reveal gender, household structure, health, education, and wealth as central drivers of exclusion of older workers, often interacting in complex ways (Alecu et al., 2025). For example, there is a clear correlation between health limitations and the economic vulnerability of older workers in Europe: workers facing significant health challenges indicate the highest levels of mental and physical exhaustion after work, worry more often about their future economic situation and report more difficulties in making ends meet (Vasile et al., 2025). Moreover, both economic constraints and health limitations influence the timing of exit of older workers: financial stability allows for greater control over one's retirement timing in contrast to low income, which leads to extended employment or early retirement with insufficient resources (Vasile et al., 2025). This issue will become increasingly challenging as pension reforms are eliminating a clear

² Council Directive [2000/78/EC](#) of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation and Council Directive [2000/43/EC](#) of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin.

statutory retirement age and making income security more dependent on the duration of one's ability to work. The COVID-19 pandemic already introduced new vulnerabilities, particularly affecting older women's risk of involuntary exit (Alecú et al., 2025).

Addressing the challenges that ageing populations face in the workforce requires a targeted support for longer working lives and a stronger focus on creating health-promoting workplaces for older workers. Policies that promote the extended participation of older workers such as health screenings, active living and ergonomic approaches can help keep aging workforces healthy and engaged. The Council Directive 89/391/EEC harmonises occupational health services across EU member states for better health and safety standards, although its implementation varies at a national level (Hämäläinen, 2020).

2.7. Wealth can mitigate vulnerability

Another target of the European Commission is to reduce the number of people at risk of poverty by at least 15 million by 2030 (European Commission, 2021). The research found that the economic context in which individuals live can impact labour market participation and retirement decisions. For example, a higher level of wealth is linked to a reduced likelihood of being excluded from the labour market (Alecú et al., 2025). The region where one lives matters as well, for example, women living in a wealthier region tend to have a higher probability of employment (Vivoli et al., 2024). Wealth appears to mitigate other vulnerabilities, such as poor health and gender, significantly reducing their negative effects among individuals with greater economic resources. To protect against (in-work) poverty and inequalities, minimum wages play an important role. However, after a substantial decline in 2022, real wages started to grow in the EU from the second half of 2023 though remain below pre-pandemic level (European Commission, 2025b).

2.8. Care responsibilities shape gendered inequality in the labour market

PATHS2INCLUDE research found people with caregiving responsibilities to be among the most vulnerable in terms of labour market participation (Vivoli et al., 2024). Care responsibilities, particularly informal care within families, present a significant challenge to activation, hiring, employment, and extended working lives, especially for women. Caregiving responsibilities can lead to fragmented employment trajectories resulting in lower retirement savings and greater financial insecurity in older age, especially for women.

Results from another part of the research show a gendered parenthood penalty where mothers, especially single mothers, face significant disadvantages in hiring processes (Buttler et al., 2025). This is particularly the case when women are applying for demanding jobs. The research also found that care-based discrimination occurs less in organisations offering flexible work arrangements and/or that have implemented diversity policy measures, which particularly benefits single mothers.

2.9. The future of work presents both opportunities and challenges for vulnerable groups

Digitalisation offers opportunities for flexibility and accessibility, but it also introduces barriers and exacerbates existing inequalities for at-risk groups. First, widening skill gaps, as a result of digitisation and automation, risk deepening existing wage inequalities which would disproportionately affect less educated and medium-skilled workers (Valls et al., 2024). Second, some gender disparities persist, with the widespread use of non-voluntary remote work further exacerbating stress and role conflict among mothers (Beckel & Fisher, 2022). Third, older workers seem to be more likely to retire early and experience the negative consequences of work intensification due to technological developments (Valls et al., 2024). In conclusion, the impact on carers, people with disabilities, older workers and migrant workers underlines the need for targeted policy responses (see also Magda & Krząkała, 2025).

3. Policy recommendations for shaping inclusive labour markets

The following key measures emerged from PATHS2INCLUDE findings and should be considered closely in the review of the Action Plan on the European Pillar of Social Rights, with the aim to make labour market measures more inclusive in policy and practice. These are relevant for both EU-level actions (policy, data and funding) as well as national and sub-national actions to support the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights, namely for public authorities, statistics institutes, Public Employment Services and Non-Governmental Organisations providing employment support, as well as social partners. EU funding programmes can also support these changes, either through financing direct services which can benefit European workers (e.g., through the ESF+) or through transfer of innovation and transnational exchanges (e.g., through the EaSI programme for employment and social innovation) (Rossenbacker & Gosme, 2025).

- **Invest in skills and training programmes tailored to the needs of vulnerable populations.** Instead of merely focusing on providing training to highly skilled individuals, training and education initiatives should be available to all at-risk groups, including people with health limitations, to mitigate the negative effects of existing disadvantages on their attachment to the labour market.
- **Invest in comprehensive data collection** to capture the employment dynamics and experiences of at-risk groups in a way that allows for cross-country comparisons and intersectional analysis. This comprehensive data collection involves expanding existing surveys to include more detailed information on socio-demographic characteristics, health and disabilities, and migration trajectories, in addition to factors that may influence employment outcomes, such as caregiving responsibilities. Longitudinal studies with larger

sample sizes allow for monitoring the effectiveness of policies over time and understanding the complex interactions between the various factors that influence employment decisions and outcomes in the present and the future of work.

- **Design policies with an intersectional approach** by targeting overlapping vulnerabilities stemming from individual characteristics, including age, health limitations, gender and caregiving responsibilities. By recognising and addressing the complex interplay of individual vulnerabilities and regional economic conditions, future labour market interventions can more effectively promote inclusion and social cohesion across the EU.
- **Ensure the full implementation and compliance with Directives 2000/78/EC** on equal treatment in employment and occupation and 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin.
- **Encourage and support organisations to adopt concrete, actionable diversity policy measures** such as inclusive hiring practices, mentoring programmes, and diversity management training while engaging managers in diversity efforts to mitigate biases in recruitment processes. Policy makers should also create (financial) incentives and support mechanisms to drive such workplace changes.
- **Expand flexible work arrangements** to facilitate work-life balance for parents and carers, as well as prevent care-based discrimination of (single) mothers. Moreover, interventions that enhance flexibility, inclusion, and support for care responsibilities, can additionally protect older workers. The uptake of these flexible and inclusive work arrangements (e.g., through public incentives or regulatory frameworks) should be particularly supported in sectors where discrimination is most pronounced.
- **Establish health-promoting workplaces** for enabling older workers to remain in employment longer and reduce their economic vulnerability. Support the implementation of Council Directive 89/391/EEC to mainstream occupational health services across Europe.
- **Ensure adequate minimum wages**, in a way that satisfies the needs of workers and their families in the light of national economic and social conditions, whilst safeguarding access to employment and incentives to seek work. Workers have the right to fair wages that provide for a decent standard of living. In-work poverty shall be prevented. All wages shall be set in a transparent and predictable way according to national practices and respecting the autonomy of the social partners.
- **Implement adequately paid leave for workers with caregiving responsibilities** enabling them to take time off work without losing income and thereby reducing financial stress and allowing better balance between caregiving duties and employment.

Taken together, these results underscore the importance of intersectional and adaptive policy responses: while structural vulnerabilities persist, well-designed interventions in the context of the European Pillar of Social Rights, particularly those that enhance flexibility, inclusion, and well-being, can play a decisive role in improving labour market outcomes of people in vulnerable situations.

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